

A Comparative Kinetic Study on the Effect of Solvents on Ion-Dipole Type of Reaction : Acid Hydrolysis of Amyl Formate in Aquo-DMSO, Aquo-propan-2-ol, Aquo-acetone, Aquo-dioxan and Aquo-ethanol Media

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Amyl formate has been acid hydrolysed in different aquo-organic co-solvents at varying composition and temperatures. The variation in specific rate constant and dielectric constant values have been determined at all the temperatures and composition of organic co-solvents used. The kinetic parameters have been evaluated. A reasonable interpretation of the experimental data has been given.

A review of literature relating to the solvent effect of ion-dipole type of reactions emphasises for further study in this regard. Although the behaviour regarding the reorganisation of the solvent surrounding the reacting substances and transition state of solvent molecules has somewhat been estimated and understood in aqueous system, however, little progress has been observed. The present work is a general acid-catalysed reaction according to the supporting evidence by Bronsted and Jones¹.

Results and Discussion

The specific rate constant values ($k \times 10^3$) for acid hydrolysis of amyl formate in the aquo-organic cosolvents have been calculated following first order kinetics (Table 1). In all the cases, k values decrease with increasing percentage composition of the respective organic cosolvent at a fixed temperature, and increase with increasing temperature at a fixed percentage composition. A fall in the rate with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium has been observed which is in accordance with the prediction made by Ingold² as well as Laidler and Landskroener³. The similar trend in the rate of hydrolysis of carboxylic acid esters in dipolar aprotic solvents has been reported by various workers⁴.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT ($k \times 10^3$, min^{-1}) FOR ACID HYDROLYSIS OF AMYL FORMATE IN VARIOUS AQUO-ORGANIC COSOLVENT AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND COMPOSITION

Temp. °C	% of DMSO (v/v)					
	30	40	50	60	70	80
20	0.69	0.61	0.57	0.48	0.41	0.35
25	0.94	0.86	0.77	0.68	0.58	0.49
30	1.30	1.17	1.04	0.93	0.79	0.70
35	1.74	1.57	1.48	1.36	1.22	1.08
	% of propan-2-ol (v/v)					
	30	40	50	60	70	
20	1.9	1.8	1.7	1.5	1.4	
25	2.2	2.1	1.9	1.7	1.6	
30	2.7	2.5	2.2	2.0	1.9	
35	3.2	2.8	2.6	2.3	2.1	
	% of acetone (v/v)					
	30	40	50	60	70	80
20	1.16	1.03	0.89	0.78	0.66	0.51
25	1.55	1.33	1.13	0.98	0.82	0.62
30	2.01	1.70	1.43	1.21	1.02	0.76
35	2.68	2.11	1.70	1.45	1.21	0.90
	% of 1,4-dioxan (v/v)					
	30	40	50	60	70	
20	2.1	1.9	1.8	1.6	1.5	
25	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.0	1.8	
30	3.2	2.9	2.6	2.4	2.2	
35	3.9	3.5	3.2	2.9	2.5	
	% of ethanol (v/v)					
	30	40	50	60	70	
20	2.1	1.9	1.8	1.6	1.5	
25	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.0	1.8	
30	3.2	2.9	2.6	2.4	2.2	
35	3.9	3.5	3.2	2.9	2.5	

Table 2 presents the values of dielectric constant of various organic cosolvents at different composition and temperatures. It decreases with increasing percentage composition and temperature. The trend is obeyed in all cases of the solvents. Since decrease in rate is observed with decreasing percentage composition of the respective organic cosolvent at a fixed temperature, so the activated complex is more polar than the reactants.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF VARIOUS ORGANIC COSOLVENTS AT DIFFERENT COMPOSITION AND TEMPERATURES

Temp °C	% of DMSO (v/v)					
	30	40	50	60	70	80
20	78.93	77.91	76.31	73.89	70.28	65.25
25	77.12	76.11	74.55	72.25	68.77	63.85
30	75.38	74.38	72.88	70.68	67.32	62.55
35	73.70	72.71	71.25	69.14	65.90	61.25
% of propan-2-ol (v/v)						
	30	40	50	60	70	
20	62.0	55.15	48.1	40.6	33.4	
25	60.18	54.25	46.9	39.55	32.5	
30	58.7	52.5	45.5	38.5	31.6	
35	57.2	51.05	43.0	37.5	30.5	
% of acetone (v/v)						
	30	40	50	60	70	80
20	65.27	59.47	53.22	46.64	39.74	32.70
25	63.81	58.13	51.94	45.49	38.83	32.15
30	62.22	56.67	50.67	44.35	37.81	31.10
35	60.77	55.37	49.45	43.26	36.92	30.34
% of 1,4-dioxan (v/v)						
	40	50	60	70		
20	43.63	34.60	26.05	17.78		
25	41.47	33.65	25.35	17.15		
30	41.22	32.65	24.57	16.75		
35	40.05	31.65	23.85	16.16		
% of ethanol (v/v)						
	30	40	50	60	70	
20	65.5	59.8	54.1	48.08	42.08	
25	63.96	58.3	52.6	46.80	40.95	
30	62.5	56.9	51.4	45.53	39.75	
35	61.0	55.6	50.1	44.40	38.78	

Table 3 shows the comparative values of iso-composition activation energy (E_c). Except for DMSO, in all the cases, E_c values decrease with increasing percentage composition of the organic cosolvent which is indicative of the fact that the activated state is more solvated than the initial state in these cases. It is further supported by decreasing value of ΔS^* with increasing percentage composition of propan-2-ol, acetone, 1,4-dioxan and ethanol respectively. In

case of DMSO, the values of E_c and ΔS^* are found to increase with increasing percentage composition of DMSO. It is assumed that formate ion offers the tendency of more hindrance in snatching water molecules by DMSO in comparison to the charged dipolar activated state and hence the initial state is more solvated than the activated state.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF E_c (kJ mol^{-1}), ΔH^* (kJ mol^{-1}) and ΔS^* ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$) FOR ACID HYDROLYSIS OF AMYL FORMATE IN VARIOUS AQUO-ORGANIC COSOLVENTS MEDIA AT DIFFERENT SOLVENT COMPOSITION

	% of DMSO (v/v)					
	30	40	50	60	70	80
E_c	46.94	48.87	51.55	54.22	56.57	61.09
ΔH^*	45.69	46.15	48.03	50.33	53.64	58.45
ΔS^*	-182.96	-182.84	-181.50	-170.54	-160.83	-143.35
% of propan-2-ol (v/v)						
	30	40	50	60	70	
E_c	26.40	24.52	22.64	20.75	18.83	
ΔH^*	24.21	23.26	21.55	20.17	19.20	
ΔS^*	-248.07	-252.30	-258.65	-263.93	-267.78	
% of acetone (v/v)						
	30	40	50	60	67	80
E_c	44.35	37.78	35.10	32.64	30.58	29.12
ΔH^*	38.49	34.77	30.54	27.91	26.74	26.15
ΔS^*	-203.59	-217.18	-232.88	-244.18	-249.49	-252.76
% of 1,4-dioxan (v/v)						
	40	50	60	70		
E_c	56.07	51.88	46.70	43.93		
ΔH^*	55.98	51.46	47.39	43.53		
ΔS^*	-137.9	-154.14	-168.82	-182.84		
% of ethanol (v/v)						
	30	40	50	60	70	
E_c	33.68	32.43	30.29	28.87	26.53	
ΔH^*	31.51	30.46	28.63	27.85	26.28	
ΔS^*	-222.67	-227.07	-233.97	-237.19	-243.30	

The values of ΔH^* and ΔS^* are tabulated in Table 3 for acid hydrolysis of amyl formate in various aquo-organic cosolvents at varying % composition. It is evident that the values of ΔH^* and ΔS^* decrease with increasing percentage composition of organic cosolvents except DMSO. The reverse trend is observed in case of DMSO.

Aqueous DMSO has been termed as TNAN type of binary system as reported in various communications⁵. Intermolecular association of this type of solvent is often supposed to occur in such type of binary system. Parker and Tomilinson⁶ pointed out the breakdown of water-water interaction by adding DMSO as a cosolvent in it. Isokinetic relationship is maintained in

all the cases by getting linear plots in accordance with Barclay-Butler rule⁷. Negligible change in ΔG^\ddagger is noticed with increasing percentage composition of each aquo-organic cosolvent at a fixed temperature.

Following Wolford⁸, iso-dielectric activation energy (E_D) values have been calculated in order to annul the effect of dielectric variation on activation energy (Table 4). E_D values have been found to increase for acid hydrolysis of amyl formate in aquo-propan-2-ol, aquo-acetone, aquo-dioxan and aquo-ethanol media, whereas in case of DMSO, it decreases with increasing dielectric constant of the medium. It can, therefore, be concluded that (i) the value of k decreases for a particular temperature and percentage composition of organic cosolvent (v/v) in the following order of solvents : 1,4-dioxan > ethanol > acetone > propan-2-ol > DMSO, (ii) the value of dielectric constant decreases in the following order of solvents : DMSO > ethanol > acetone > propan-2-ol > dioxan, and (iii) the values of E_c , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger and decrease for a particular percentage composition of organic cosolvent in the following order of solvents : dioxan > acetone > ethanol > propan-2-ol. As far as the trend of change in E_c , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger is concerned, it is quite reverse in DMSO than that of the rest of the organic cosolvents in the present study.

Experimental

AnalaR and standard grade chemicals (B.D.H., E. Merck) were used. The purified organic solvents taken for the present study as aquo-organic cosolvent mixture had the following composition (% v/v) : DMSO and acetone : 30, 40, 50, 60, 70 and 80; and propan-2-ol, 1,4-dioxan and ethanol : 30, 40, 50, 60 and 70.

Acid-catalysed hydrolysis of amyl formate in the above aquo-organic cosolvents was performed by the usual method at 20, 25, 30 and 35°. The tire used was standard baryta solution. Dielectric constants for different solvent mixtures were evaluated⁹.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF ISO-DIELECTRIC ACTIVATION ENERGY, (E_D) FOR ACID HYDROLYSIS OF AMYL FORMATE IN VARIOUS AQUO-ORGANIC COSOLVENT MEDIA AT DIFFERENT DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF THE MEDIUM

Dielectric constant of DMSO	64	66	68	70	72	
E_D (kJ mol ⁻¹)	59.25	57.61	57.40	54.68	53.93	
Dielectric constant of propan-2-ol	34.5	38.5	42.5	46.5	50.5	54.5
E_D (kJ mol ⁻¹)	21.7	22.6	23.3	24.7	26.5	28.0
Dielectric constant of acetone	40	44	48	52	56	60
E_D (kJ mol ⁻¹)	37.07	37.32	32.95	39.87	40.42	43.56
Dielectric constant of 1,4-dioxan	22	24	26	28	30	32
E_D (kJ mol ⁻¹)	43.43	45.14	46.86	48.58	50.33	52.05
Dielectric constant of ethanol	42	46	50	54	58	62
E_D (kJ mol ⁻¹)	28.90	30.32	31.75	33.14	34.35	35.77

The various activation parameters¹⁰ along with the precision and reliability of results have been obtained by the usual methods.

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